

USE OF MIXED METHODS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

Xamzayev Akmal Amirovich

Senior teacher of interfaculty department of foreign languages
of Jizakh State pedagogical university

Abstract

This article describes the use of interactive methods in teaching foreign languages, traditional methods, mixed methods and non-traditional methods, their specific features. The mixed method in the study of a foreign language is considered as an example.

Keywords: methodology, innovation, foreign language, communication, skills, qualifications, didactics, intercultural communication.

I. Introduction

The development of modern education has led to a new direction of innovative pedagogy. Innovative - means "introduction (dissemination) of innovation" in English. The socio-psychological aspect of innovation was developed by American researcher E. Rodgers. He studied the classification of participants in the innovation process, their attitudes to innovation, and more. In science, the concepts of novelty and innovation are different. "Innovation" means a tool, a new method, technique, technology. Innovation is a process of education that develops in certain stages. The development of world science is accelerating day by day. It is this positive development that has affected our country. Advanced innovative technologies are being introduced into the world of science. As a result, the President's announcement of this year as the "Year of Youth Support and Public Health" has further increased the responsibility of the youth of our country. It is safe to say that the widespread introduction of advanced, modern and innovative technologies in the field of education has opened a wide range of opportunities and milestones for young people learning a foreign language. Language learning is one of the most important areas of human society. Language, which is a means of communication, can be practiced in a natural environment, in the family, in the community, or in an organized way. Knowledge of linguistic phenomena is taught in theory. Knowledge of languages, especially multilingualism, is of great importance in today's world of international relations. Pupils and students studying in our country usually learn three languages. These languages are referred to by special names. These are: native language, second language, and foreign language. Mother tongue is the first language that plays a special role in the formation of thinking. When it comes to a second language, it is considered the language of brothers and sisters of other nationalities. The subject of the methodology is the process and methods of teaching through a foreign language, the science of foreign language teaching, the study of teacher and student activities.

Basic concepts of methodology - method, method, principle. Didactics - what do we teach? is the content of teaching. Methodology - how do we teach? teaching methods and techniques. The concept of method is derived from the Greek-Latin word *metodos* - "method", which means a way to a specific goal. The narrow and broad meanings of the term can be found in various literatures. The term "methodology" in a narrow sense refers to a concept related to the specific teaching process of education. It is interpreted as a managed learning process that

includes instructions related to lesson planning and preparation of teaching materials. The term “method” in a broad sense refers to the selection, stratification, and distribution of teaching materials.

A foreign language teaching method is a set of teacher and student activities that ensure the achievement of practical, general, educational and developmental goals of foreign language teaching. The term method is used to mean "a set of teaching methods" and "direction of education". The first is used in the theory of education in the sense of process methods, the second sense can be found in works on the history of teaching methods. For example, the translation method of foreign language teaching, the correct method, the comparative method, the traditional method, the intensive method, and so on.

The method of translation is mainly in two forms, called grammar-translation and text-translation methods. From the point of view of grammar-translation method, a foreign language is studied for general educational purposes. Grammar exercises are designed to develop the learner's logical thinking. Explaining grammatical knowledge is considered to be the main goal of education. The main principles of this method are:

1. Language learning is based on written speech.
2. The subject of study is grammar, and the vocabulary is chosen accordingly. Grammar exercises were the main way to work.
3. First, the grammatical rule is memorized, and then it is recommended to make sentences based on the rules.
4. The grammatical form and meaning of the words are revealed through literal translation.
5. Language material is mastered through literal translation and dry memorization.
6. Limited to individual memorization of words outside the context.

Method without translation. Various aspects of this method have been known throughout history. They can be divided into two main groups: natural and correct methods. Learning a foreign language in a natural way should be similar to learning a native language. The idea that the main purpose of the method is to learn to read and write by learning to speak a foreign language is formed for practical purposes. The most important of the principles included in the natural method is to create a language environment. There are different approaches to the practical application of the proposed methodological principles. This can be clearly seen in the creative work of the representatives of the method.

The goals of listening comprehension have changed. Telling and controlling what he heard also took on a different tone. This method, depending on the purpose, distinguishes the following types of listening comprehension:

- Understand the main content of the text in the broadest sense, without paying attention to some details;
- This method is used when accurate information is important, such as the need for weather for a particular location, the announcement of train arrivals and departures, and so on.

It is precisely this knowledge that we retain in our minds, the study of information in communicative didactics, which, from the concept of ‘communication’, is semantically intertwined with the term ‘intercultural communication’.

The term intercultural communication is now widely used in foreign language teaching methods. It is this concept that we can use in a variety of contexts. In fact: Intercultural communication is the dialogue between people of different cultures about their social origins, mentality, national character, lifestyle, customs, value system, and so on. In this process, students should be educated and developed in the spirit of respect, tolerance for the culture of the country being studied, and a correct understanding of the culture of another country.

In order for a teacher to be successful, not only subject, pedagogical and psychological knowledge, but also another special feature - communication skills and competencies - are absolutely necessary.

Pedagogical communication is a interaction between a teacher and a student, which is based on the exchange of information, primarily educational information, helps to understand the partner of pedagogical communication, as well as to carry out collaborative activities. Information is conveyed both verbally and verbally. The teacher should play a key role in the pedagogical communication process and be a role model for the students. This is judged by its communicative culture. The communicative culture of the teacher is a professional-pedagogical dialogue with the subjects of his educational process. can unconditionally ensure the achievement of their goals. The social significance of communicative culture is that the teacher who masters it can create a positive psychological climate in the interaction of all subjects of the educational process, implement the important principles of modernization of education - humanism and democratization. The personal significance is that the educator with a communicative culture has high self-confidence, enjoys the communication built with the pupil, feels free in the chosen work activity.

A number of personal qualities required for a culture of pedagogical communication include honesty, openness, self-control, assertiveness, sincerity, perseverance, endurance, and tactics. The teacher needs to shape not only their communication skills, but also the intercultural communication of the students. The teacher is required to have a good knowledge of the psychology of students, their social views, the process of socialization. It is important to note that the success or failure of pedagogical, intercultural communication ultimately depends on what approach the educator chooses and how he or she can apply it in practice. Not only sound education but his alertness and dedication too are most required. Of course, this result can be achieved only through the correct organization of the lesson, the widespread use of advanced, modern innovative technologies. The innovative activity of the educator includes the analysis and evaluation of innovation, the formation, implementation and analysis of the goals and concepts of future actions, the evaluation of effectiveness. From all the above considerations, it is clear that in order to achieve such positive results, the educator must resort to the next step in foreign language teaching, ie "exercise technology", and its practical application leads to the acquisition of knowledge and skills. . Learning a foreign language is a multifaceted discipline, in the process of which a person experiences complex psychological changes. In particular, there is a process of comparing a native language with a foreign language. Different teaching methods and technologies are used in this process. With the help of modern pedagogical technologies, comparative teaching of a foreign language

with the native language gives effective results. Teaching a foreign language requires knowledge of its methodology. Methods and technologies play an important role in learning a foreign language. There are different methods of methodological science in the organization of the lesson. The most widely used methods of foreign language teaching are: the method of communicative didactics, the method of organizing intercultural communication and the method of organizing exercises. The three methods are closely related and complementary. Because the science of methodology is related to the science of didactics, the study of a foreign language is based on communicativeness, and the method of communicative didactics emerges.

In the process of applying the method of communicative didactics, the teacher's method of forming intercultural communication is also formed. Learning a foreign language helps you to learn the culture of another country. Exercise technology is important for learning a foreign language. Exercise is the best way to master all the knowledge. Exercise has a positive effect not only on foreign language teaching, but also on the acquisition of knowledge in all areas. The effective organization of the lesson, in which the role of pedagogical activity and modern pedagogical technologies is invaluable. It is important to organize the process of learning a foreign language with a communicative approach, to bring the next stage to the level of intercultural communication, and to achieve such results, the last step is to pay attention to "exercise technology". In order to effectively organize the process of teaching a foreign language, it is necessary to acquire knowledge of modern pedagogical information and communication technologies.

References:

1. Raxmanova, M. K. (2019). Social activism in students theoretical and methodological bases of development. Public Education, (1), 24-29.
2. Krashen, Stephen Second language Acquisition. New York 1987. Oxford
3. Nunan, D Designing Tasks for the Communicative Classroom. Cambridge 1993
4. Xamzayev, A. (2020). The background of teaching grammar through games. Архив Научных Публикаций JSPI, 1(88). извлечено от https://science.iedu.uz/index.php/archive_jspi/article/view/7092
5. Xamzayev, A. (2020). Different Permanent Associations That Express Public Life In English and The Problems Of Translating Them Into Uzbek Language. Архив Научных Публикаций JSPI, 1(90). извлечено от https://science.iedu.uz/index.php/archive_jspi/article/view/6989